

Phosphorus Containing Polymethin Dyes

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In our present investigation several phosphocyanines and merophosphimines have been prepared from a fixed basic nucleus cyclopentadienylene triphenyl phosphorane¹ and various basic and acidic nuclei respectively. Utilising the absorption maxima data of these dyes certain generalisations on the influence of structural changes on absorption and the relative basicity of cyclopentadienylene triphenyl phosphorane as compared to other basic nuclei have been determined.

The present work describes the preparations of dimethin, tetramethin and hexamethin phosphocyanines and monomethin, trimethin and pentamethin merophosphimines from the fixed basic nucleus cyclopentadienylene triphenyl phosphorane with various variable basic and acidic nuclei.

The dimethin phosphocyanines were prepared by condensing the various acetanilido vinyl derivatives of 2-methyl quaternary salts, prepared by heating the salt with diphenyl formamidine in acetic anhydride², with the phosphorane in alcohol and triethylamine.

The tetramethin phosphocyanines were prepared by refluxing the various acetanilido butadienyl derivatives of 2-methyl quaternary salts, prepared by heating the salt with beta anilino acrolein anil hydrochloride in acetic anhydride²; with phosphorane in alcohol and triethylamine.

Similarly the hexamethin phosphocyanines were prepared by the condensation of acetanilido hexatrienyl intermediates of various 2-methyl quaternary salts with the phosphorane as above.

The phosphocyanines conform to the structure (I)

The monomethin merophosphimines were prepared by condensing the ethoxy methylene derivatives of different ketomethylene compounds with phosphorane in alcohol and triethylamine.

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Similarly the trimethin and pentamethin merophosphinines were prepared by condensing the methoxy allylidene and acetanilido pentadienylidene intermediates of various ketomethylene compounds with the phosphorane as above.

The merophosphinines conform to the following structure (II)

The relative basicity of cyclopentadienylene triphenyl phosphorane as compared to other basic nuclei has been evaluated with the help of Brooker's deviation factor³⁻⁴. The relative decreasing order of basicity conforms to the following sequence.

Lepidine > Quinaldine > Benz(f) quinoline > 4-phenyl thiazole > Benzothiazole > Benzoxazole > Phosphorane.

Similarly the relative order of decreasing basicity of various heterocyclic nuclei used in the preparation of phosphocyanines and relative order of decreasing acidity of ketomethylene compounds used in the preparation of merophosphinines have been evaluated which is in excellent agreement with our previous findings⁴.

Relative Basicity—

Lepidine > Quinaldine > 4-phenyl thiazole > α and β -naphtha-thiazole > Benzothiazole > α and β -naphthoxazole > Benzoxazole > Thiazoline.

Relative Acidity—

Thiazolone > Oxazolone > Indane 1,3-dione > Thiobarbituric acid > Pyrazolone > Rhodanine.

EXPERIMENTAL

2-(Cyclopentadienylene triphenyl phosphorane) 3-methyl benzothiazolium iodide: Cyclopentadienylene triphenyl phosphorane (3.28 g.) and 2-methyl mercapto benzothiazolium iodide (3.23 g.) in absolute alcohol (20 cc) and triethylamine (2 drops) were refluxed for 20 minutes. The solid which separated was crystallised from ethyl alcohol. Yield—55%; M.P.—210°. Found C, 77.60; H, 4.06; P, 5.06. $C_{31}H_{25}NSP$ requires C, 77.71; H, 4.16 and P, 5.15%.

The dye absorbs at 415 $m\mu$ in ethanol.

(Cyclopentadienylene triphenyl phosphorane) (3-methyl-benzothiazole) 2-2' dimethin cyanine iodide: Cyclopentadienylene triphenyl phosphorane (0.33 g.) and 2-(2'-acetanilido vinyl)

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benzothiazolium iodide (0.38 g.) were refluxed with absolute alcohol and triethyl amine (2 drops) for five minutes. The dye which separated after cooling was crystallised from alcohol.

The analytical data, m.p. etc., of the related phosphocyanines derived from various acetanilido vinyl and acetanilido butadienyl derivatives are recorded in the Table I.

TABLE I

Nature of the nucleus 'B'	Value of 'n'	Yield %	M.P. °C	λ max in $m\mu$	% Phosphorus	
					Found	Calcd.
Thiazoline	1	62	238	458	—	—
-do-	2	60	250	560	5.08	5.13
Benzoxazole	1	59	235	470	4.97	5.07
-do-	2	62	230	570	—	—
alpha Naphthoxazole	1	60	235	495	4.62	4.69
-do-	2	59	255	590	4.48	4.51
beta Naphthoxazole	1	60	215	495	4.63	4.69
-do-	2	55	240	590	—	—
Benzothiazole	1	85	225	518	4.89	4.95
-do-	2	90	223	610	4.67	4.74
alpha Naphtha-thiazole	1	70	140	530	4.57	4.60
-do-	2	65	190	620	—	—
beta Naphtha-thiazole	1	70	180	530	4.51	4.60
-do-	2	65	200	620	4.39	4.41
4-Phenyl thiazole	1	65	175	510	4.70	4.75
-do-	2	50	202	600	4.51	4.56
Quinoline-2	1	60	250	550	4.86	4.99
-do-	2	55	175	635	4.60	4.79
Quinoline-4	1	70	250	580	4.92	4.99
-do-	2	60	200	670	4.68	4.79

(Cyclopentadienylene triphenyl phosphorane) (3-methyl benzothiazole)-2-2'-hexamethin cyanine iodide: The phosphorane (0.33 g.) and acetanilido hexatrienyl intermediate of 2-methyl benzothiazole methiodide were refluxed with alcohol and triethylamine and the dye was isolated as above. Yield—68%; M.P.—255°. (Found C, 65.30; H, 4.52; P, 4.50. $C_{37}H_{31}NSPI$ requires C, 65.39; H, 4.56; P, 4.56%).

The dye shows absorption maximum at 740 $m\mu$ in ethanol.

(Cyclopentadienylene triphenyl phosphorane) (1-phenyl 3-methyl pyrazolone) monomethin merophosphinine: The phosphorane (0.33 g.) and 4-ethoxy methylene 1-phenyl 3-methyl pyrazolone (0.21 g.) were refluxed with absolute alcohol (10 cc) and two drops of triethylamine for five minutes. It was cooled and the solid which separated was crystallised from absolute alcohol.

The analytical data, m.p. etc., of the related merophosphinines derived from different ketomethylene compound intermediates are recorded in the Table II.

TABLE II
Merophosphinines derived from the phosphorane

Nature of the nucleus 'B'	Value of 'n'	Yield %	M.P. °C	λ max in $m\mu$	% Phosphorus	
					Found	Calcd.
Rhodanine	0	68	165*	480	5.59	5.68
-do-	1	62	170	550	—	—
-do-	2	65	145	680	5.07	5.18
Pyrazolone	0	57	151	445	6.00	6.07
-do-	1	65	166*	550	5.72	5.77
-do-	2	68	188*	675	—	—
Thiobarbituric acid	0	62	160	460	4.82	4.90
-do-	1	55	198*	570	—	—
-do-	2	37	160	665	—	—
Indane 1 : 3 dione	0	72	152	460	6.39	6.43
-do-	1	69	160	565	6.01	6.10
-do-	2	70	182	670	5.76	5.80
Oxazolone	0	49	153*	470	6.18	6.23
Thiazolone	0	51	140*	494	5.59	5.67

* Denoted decomposition.

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